

Use of Résumé for Researchers (R4R)-like Narrative CV: Reviewer Guidance synthesis

Purpose

This reviewer guidance synthesis aims to provide a summary of the commonalities of the [Résumé for Researchers](#) (R4R)-like narrative CV reviewer guidance for peer reviewers and panel/committee members as used by some members of the [Joint Funders Group](#) in January 2022.

Table 1: Summary of findings

Across a sample of 4 funders in January 2022 the following was observed:

Funder	Guidance accompanied by other resources	Location of reviewer guidance	Training provided	Guidance tailored for different calls	Evaluation undertaken
1	Yes	- Reviewer guidance document - Reviewer form	No	No	Yes
2	No	- Reviewer form	No	No	Yes
3	Yes	- Reviewer guidance document - Briefing video	No	Yes	Yes
4	No	- Committee guidance document - Peer reviewer guidance document (in development)	No	Yes	No

Synthesis of findings

Provision of guidance for reviewers

- All funders sampled are using an R4R-Like CV in at least one funding opportunity and are providing guidance for reviewers to assess the CV. A number of other funders (not included within the table) are developing guidance.
- Three funders provide guidance within a reviewer guidance document, and two funders provide guidance within the reviewer form (a document completed by the reviewer containing their assessment).
- Two funders accompany their guidance with a video resources they have developed, no funders indicated signposting to resources generated by others.

Training provided on the guidance

- Two funders are currently considering developing their training provision.

Tailoring reviewer guidance for different funding calls

- Two funders' tailor their guidance for different funding calls; one noted that guidance was tailored based on different career stages the funding calls are aimed at.

Evaluation

- Insights from evaluations undertaken by group members include the need for training and more detailed guidance on why the funder is using an R4R-Like CV, and the principles of what the funder are trying to achieve in its use.

Common features and key considerations in developing guidance

- Funders have different motivations for implementing a R4R-Like CV; it is helpful to be explicit to reviewers as to why as an organisation you are taking this assessment process.

- Ensuring the guidance is straightforward and not too long and the process is streamlined.
- Steering the reviewers to consider the information submitted in the R4R-Like CV.
- The common features in the guidance have been pulled together in the [R4R-Like CV Reviewer Guidance Starter Guide](#).

Next Steps

- There is an aspiration to revisit the reviewer guidance synthesis with updated information in light of reviews and evaluations.

Version Control

<u>Version Number</u>	<u>Status</u>	<u>Revision Date</u>	<u>Author(s)</u>	<u>Summary of Changes</u>
1.0	Complete	March 2022	Joint Funders Group	New resource created